

PECULIARITIES OF SPEECH TECHNIQUE AND SPEECH CULTURE OF A PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHER

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Abstract: This article highlights the emergence and development of the art of public speaking, the important aspects that a primary school teacher should acquire within the framework of speech technique and public speaking art.

Key words: Oratory, ancient Greece, "King of arts, external speech, internal speech, teacher's speech culture, monologic speech, dialogic speech, communicative speech, sound, diction, rhythmicity, articulation.

In the pedagogical skill of the teacher, his speech and eloquence are important. Special attention was paid to this problem in the years after independence. First of all, the ideology of national independence is important in educating the young generation in the spirit of patriotism. One of the high pillars of our ideology is the language of the nation. The Laws of our Republic "On the State Language", "On Education", "National Program of Personnel Training" and other documents recognize the formation of feelings of love and affection towards one's mother tongue in the upbringing of a mature generation. . In the spiritual and educational education of the young generation, the speech of the teacher, his art of oratory receives special attention. First President I.A. Karimov in his speech at the 9th session of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 29, 1997 stated that "A specialist who cannot express his opinion fluently, beautifully and concisely in his mother tongue should be, first of all, a leader It is difficult to understand and to justify those sitting on his chair today. When considering how important the formation of the teacher's speech culture is in his professional activity, first of all, it

is necessary to know the history of the origin of the art of speaking. Professional public speaking has a long history in Greece, Central Asia, and India. According to historians (Apresyan G.Z.), the art of oratory was founded in Greece in the 7th century BC. In ancient Greece, educating children was entrusted to philosophers. They are mature representatives of the art of oratory, they penetrated people's thoughts and minds with their beautiful words, loud and impressive voices, and achieved great achievements in education and upbringing. Therefore, it is stated in the scientific literature that the theory of the art of oratory and speech culture, its infinite educational value, was first founded in ancient Greece. Along with epics, lyrics, drama, sculpture, music and architecture, oratory was recognized as a complex and important art form in Greece. In Greece, the art of oratory was called the "King of Arts" because of its importance in the activities related to the important social and political affairs of the state, and because it is a complex tool that strongly influences the mind and thinking of the young generation.

The 5th century BC is considered the most refined and developed period of the "Art of Oratory" in Greece. During this period, the following three rules of public speaking were intensively improved and the speaker was required to pay serious attention to them:

- to explain (a certain idea) to the listener;
- awakening the listener's thinking (thought, mind, purpose);
- attracting the listener (on the basis of creating a sense of well-being and satisfaction).

By following these laws, orators called upon people to be good, fair, loyal to their duties to the country, to follow the best human qualities, to always fulfill them, to observe the rules of manners and ethics. This was considered their main task. Such as Socrates, Plato, Dinarchus, Hyperides, Gorgias, Isocrates, Issaeus, Aeschylus, Demosthenes, Cicero, Quintilian, who deeply mastered the art of oratory in Greece and gained respect and attention in society with their beautiful and

beautiful speeches and unique works. representatives became famous statesmen of Greece.

Greek orators deeply mastered the forms and laws of oral speech, the rules of logic, such as reasoning and proof. They were able to deeply imbibe their thoughts and feelings into the minds and minds of their readers and listeners and had a dramatic impact. Each orator has been practicing incessantly, following all the laws of speech technique to become the owner of a magical voice. They considered the art of public speaking as a "tool of ideological and political struggle and education of the young generation" and proved it in their activities by demonstrating their impressive speeches.

The development of the art of oratory in our country is connected with the history of Central Asian culture, and speech culture has always had a unique position. The characteristics of the art of oratory in Central Asia were that it primarily served the interests of the regime of that time. This is evidenced by the fact that the masters of the art of oratory in this period were referred to as nadims, storytellers, masalgoys, badihagoys, qiraatkhan, problematgoys, preachers, goyandans, maddohs, qasidakhans. In Movarounnahr, the art of speaking was called preaching. Preaching, that is, preaching together with promoting the "Quran" meant the importance and meaning of the word. The word "waz" comes from the Arabic language and means admonition. A preacher is called a preacher. The art of preaching is the skill of influencing the mind and emotions of the listener, the community, and rulers in the ancient East highly valued the service of the representatives of this art.

Eastern thinkers have expressed many positive ideas in the literary heritage of mudarris about the manners of communication. From this point of view, the concept of speech culture, called "Etiquette of Speech" and "Culture of Communication", has attracted the attention of scientists and intellectuals for a very long time. Great figures such as Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Nasr Farabi, Unsurul Maoli Kayqavus, Abu Abdullah Al-Khorazmi, Mahmud Kashghari, az-Zamahshari,

Yusuf Khos Hajib, Ahmad Yugnaki, Abdurrahman Jami, Alisher Navai, addressed the issues of speech etiquette, oratory in general. They wrote works on language, vocabulary, grammar, and logic, while urging serious attention to the word.

Mastery of speech technique is important in the teacher's pedagogical activity. After all, the teacher awakens the child's feelings, provides conscious communication with students, and analytically perceives the information related to education through speech. For this, the future teacher must first thoroughly understand the secrets of speech, its influence in communication with students. In order to study the specific features of speech, it is necessary to know the requirements for speech technique. These requirements are that the speech is logically correct, clear, beautiful, bright and appropriate. The main characteristics of speech arise from these requirements:

1. Correctness and fluency of speech.
2. Clarity and effectiveness of speech.
3. Logic of speech.
4. Cleanliness and expressiveness of speech.

The correctness and fluency of the speech is its compliance with the norms of the literary language. Attention is paid to two aspects: emphasis and adherence to grammatical norms.

Accent - ensures the correct pronunciation of words.

Grammatical norm - is a set of various rules expressing the meaningfulness and meaningfulness of the speech, the change of words in the flow of speech, and the combination of content.

Clarity and effectiveness of speech is a factor of impact of meaningful speech on the listener. The teacher imparts knowledge to students based on clear facts with the fluency of words and language, and develops their skills and abilities. Clarity of the teacher's speech is a condition for a deep sense of responsibility. Accuracy is the correspondence of the subject being studied to the reality and facts expressed by the teacher. In determining the limit of accuracy, the teacher is required to be able

to use words correctly, to have a perfect knowledge of Uzbek language grammar, and to be able to pronounce correctly.

The logic of the speech - the logic of the speech depends first of all on the teacher's vocabulary, ability to think, perception skills. The teacher may know the language very well and have a wide vocabulary. But if he does not have a deep knowledge of the subject he is thinking about, if he cannot analyze his knowledge within the framework of his thinking, the art of public speaking will not work. The correct expression of the words in accordance with the subject expressed by the teacher, the matching of phrases, sentences, and texts to each other, and their subjugation to express the idea in a coherent way means that the speech is logically rich. The ideas presented to the students should be logically connected. The logic of the teacher's speech is undermined by the loss of intellectual connection and coherence between the sentences. In order to have a logical connection between the texts of the studied topic, the texts are separated by the beginning (for example, in summary; at the same time; it should be noted that etc.).

Therefore, the logicity of the teacher's speech is understood as a speech structured on the basis of a single system, the development of thoughts and opinions is consistent, and every word and phrase is used for a specific purpose.

Cleanliness and expressiveness of speech - Cleanliness of the teacher's speech is determined first of all by its expression in accordance with the norms of the literary language. The teacher's beautiful and content-rich speech is evaluated according to the fact that it is structured in accordance with the requirements of the modern Uzbek literary language and is free of non-literary language elements. The elements that destroy the purity of speech are dialecticism and barbarism. After all, these elements should not be used in the speech of the teacher in the course of the lesson and educational activity, even if they perform a certain artistic-aesthetic task in fiction. The teacher's constant inappropriate use of departmental terms, official words and phrases causes his speech to be unnatural and unreliable. As a result, the expression of ideas used by the teacher through the method of persuasion in the education of

students is damaged. The purity of speech is that it is free from various dialects and is expressed only in the eternal language. Language tools are used depending on the situation, the speech of the teacher, which is formed without dense words and phrases, is natural and sincere, it quickly reaches the heart of the listener and student. Speech activity of the teacher consists of: speaking, reading and listening. It is not appropriate for teachers with professional knowledge to speak in lively, simple language, and ordinary teachers who do not have sufficient knowledge of public speaking should not try to speak in scientific and formal language. So, the teacher-speaker is required to act according to the situation, and it is his duty to try to fully convey any idea he wants to express to the students.

Speaking in a language that students can understand, being able to convince them is one of the main conditions for a teacher. In order to do this, the teacher, as mentioned above, should have a well-defined plan of presentation in addition to a good knowledge of the subject. It is necessary to organize the thoughts in the speech in the first and second order, to connect them, to introduce the students to the plan of the speech, and to start the speech. Timing is one of the virtues of public speaking. Because the students will not get bored if the speaking period is announced and followed, if possible, a little earlier.

The statement about the expressiveness and expressiveness of speech is, in a certain sense, the conclusion of what was said about the qualities of speech. Because pointing out the qualities of a good speech, analyzing some typical mistakes in a speech, ultimately serves to form an impressive speech. There are various ways and means of conveying the ideas of the speech meaningfully to the students. They can also be called auxiliaries. For example, take humor or a story. The continuous stream of scientific and popular thought in the speech, its presentation in one ceremony can bore both the reader and any listener.

At such a time, it is very useful for the teacher to talk about humor, stories, and interesting events. It's even better if the humor is appropriate to the context of the speech. In this way, the student will be relaxed and interested in the subject

being studied. It is also appropriate to give some thoughts and comments within the scope of the speech. Such ideas are used to prove the correctness and truthfulness of the speaker's opinion, but their use should not be abused. The use of examples of literary literature, wise words, language means of expression and image in the speech will not be without benefits.

Factors such as how the teacher behaves, gestures, and even clothes during the speech process play a role in how the speech affects the students and what impression it leaves on them. Qualities such as sincerity, politeness, politeness, and respect for students make the speech attentively listened to by students.

In conclusion, mastering the art of public speaking is a complex process that requires a lot of work for primary school teachers. Sharpness, brightness and originality of the speech are necessary to arouse feelings and interest in the listener and reader, to draw his attention, to convey the content of what is being said well. Therefore, the speech of a primary education teacher should be clear and fluent, grammatically correct, obey the rules of literary pronunciation, and be coherent from beginning to end. Based on such speech, the knowledge learned reaches the student's heart. Such speech meets the requirements of cultural speech. For this, the teacher is required to constantly search and work on himself, philological knowledge and constant speech practice.

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